

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Report

Sample Name **MAG 172(0)**
Comment

Instrument maXis 4G
Method ms_nocolumn_mid_pos.m

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Measured m/z vs. theoretical m/z

Meas. m/z	#	Formula	Score	m/z	err [mDa]	err [ppm]	mSigma	rdb	e ⁻ Conf	z
391.1680	1	C 52 H 42 N 6 O 2	100.00	391.1679	-0.1	-0.3	23.8	35.0	even	2+
781.3277	1	C 52 H 41 N 6 O 2	100.00	781.3286	0.9	1.1	8.3	35.5	even	1+

Mass list

#	m/z	I %	I
1	196.0912	1.3	14303
2	210.1098	4.4	46668
3	224.1254	1.8	19129
4	228.2317	1.5	16065
5	229.1405	1.3	14005
6	240.1567	2.2	23719
7	249.1569	1.1	11940
8	254.2474	1.8	19694
9	256.2631	8.3	88868
10	257.2662	1.4	15248
11	261.1144	19.4	206727
12	261.4488	10.2	108932
13	261.7830	3.1	33028
14	263.2363	1.5	15591
15	268.2265	1.2	12403
16	270.2787	1.6	17131
17	279.2314	2.1	22313
18	280.2631	9.4	100496
19	281.2662	1.8	19519
20	282.2790	28.6	305031
21	283.2821	5.4	57746
22	284.2937	2.9	30825
23	288.2892	2.2	23645
24	290.2086	7.4	79390
25	291.2119	1.3	13390
26	292.2251	5.2	55923
27	293.2281	1.0	11196
28	294.2417	2.0	21003
29	296.2582	16.5	175698
30	297.2612	3.3	34678
31	298.2730	2.3	24887
32	304.2242	1.4	15111
33	304.2606	2.7	28795
34	306.2035	1.2	13131
35	308.2197	1.9	20264
36	310.2363	1.5	15656
37	312.2527	1.3	13687
38	316.2238	1.4	14872
39	318.2405	100.0	1066381
40	319.2435	17.6	187188
41	320.2556	27.7	295564
42	321.2586	5.4	57105
43	324.2504	1.1	11767
44	332.2191	6.0	64285
45	333.2222	1.3	13636
46	334.2349	14.2	151282
47	335.2376	2.7	29122
48	336.2505	17.6	187924
49	337.2536	3.3	34943
50	338.2657	3.6	38330
51	346.2348	4.6	49451
52	348.2139	1.5	15690
53	348.2499	1.4	14681
54	350.2297	8.1	85968
55	350.2656	1.4	14866
56	351.2321	1.8	18776
57	352.2450	4.0	43019
58	352.2818	12.4	132500
59	353.2849	2.6	27833
60	362.2296	1.3	14022
61	364.2452	4.2	45122

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#	m/z	I %	I
62	366.2244	2.7	29255
63	366.2599	1.1	11474
64	368.2397	1.1	11223
65	378.2609	3.0	31504
66	380.2400	1.3	13930
67	391.1680	31.9	340572
68	391.6694	17.3	184179
69	392.1707	4.9	52096
70	453.3425	1.3	13401
71	475.3253	29.1	309867
72	476.3282	7.4	78769
73	477.3303	1.5	15810
74	489.3654	3.2	33700
75	490.3679	1.0	11150
76	503.3446	1.1	11814
77	503.3806	1.3	13975
78	505.3600	1.4	15108
79	563.5497	1.9	20418
80	585.4586	1.3	14082
81	613.4906	9.7	103394
82	614.4934	3.9	41963
83	615.5050	4.8	51434
84	616.5071	2.0	21382
85	617.5187	1.2	13199
86	629.4847	2.3	24592
87	631.5006	3.5	37181
88	632.5027	1.5	15466
89	633.5147	1.5	16322
90	645.4798	2.2	23829
91	647.4950	2.4	25790
92	647.5311	1.4	15228
93	648.4975	1.0	11013
94	661.4751	1.3	13413
95	663.4896	1.5	16231
96	701.4928	3.8	40693
97	702.4957	1.7	18130
98	781.3277	8.2	87738
99	782.3307	4.7	50383
100	783.3335	1.4	14473

Acquisition Parameter

General	Fore Vacuum	3.36e+000 mBar	High Vacuum	9.05e-008 mBar	Source Type	ESI
	Scan Begin	75 m/z	Scan End	2000 m/z	Ion Polarity	Positive
Source	Set Nebulizer	2.0 Bar	Set Capillary	4500 V	Set Dry Gas	8.0 l/min
	Set Dry Heater	200 °C	Set End Plate Offset	-500 V		
Quadrupole	Set Ion Energy (MS only)	4.0 eV				
Coll. Cell	Collision Energy	8.0 eV	Set Collision Cell RF	600.0 Vpp	100.0 Vpp	
Ion Cooler	Set Ion Cooler Transfer Time	75.0 µs	Set Ion Cooler Pre Pulse Storage Time	10.0 µs		